

POLITICAL SCIENCES

FROM THE HISTORY OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF WAR THEORY

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Abstract

It is impossible to find a nation in the world that has existed and still exists that has not faced the trials of war in its history and has not tried to emerge from this war with fewer losses and better results. As for the ways to achieve this, after various observations and generalizations, extremely different and dissimilar views and opinions have emerged from time to time. However, since these ideas and considerations could not go beyond the level of social development of the time, of course, the issues of interest were explained in a simple way and were based more on subjective thinking. Although the conclusions of the authors of simple ideas, unscientific generalizations and theories are of historical importance, they failed to reveal the objective causes of wars and the regularities of war management. They also created misconceptions about the emergence and operation of wars. This article briefly aims to create a picture of the development of ideas and concepts about the essence and nature of war from ancient times.

Keywords: war, politics, armed force, theory of war, state, military security

Introduction

The history of military thought has very ancient roots. Even in the examples of oral creativity of the period before the discovery of writing, one can find interesting ideas about the people's war trials, the struggle of good and evil, the heroism of the people's representatives and ways to win over evil (1, p.5; 8). Even in the most ancient examples of written sources, there is a lot of historical information about the wars of the time, their conduct, management and consequences. This information leads to the conclusion that the most diverse peoples of the ancient world tried to understand the nature of wars and their regularities, and also tried to form a certain experience in this area. Because the ability to wage wars in a specific historical context was considered one of the main factors in the protection of statehood itself.

Although the earliest examples of the history of every idea to date contain different views on the causes of wars, most of these examples have viewed wars not as a chaotic, spontaneous event, but as a controlled process. In other words, the ancient intellectuals did not doubt that in order for wars to become a successful process, concrete measures must be taken, purposeful preparations must be made, and battles must be based on well-thought-out plans. In other words, providing the necessary guidance for the preparation and conduct of war was considered an integral part of such military success in ancient times.

Ancient and medieval thinkers about wars

More serious and logical approaches to understanding and comprehending the essence and nature of wars can still be found in the works of ancient Chinese thinkers and philosophers.

VI-V centuries BC, several interesting works on the theory of warfare appeared in ancient China. One of the works of special value in this regard is the "Treatise on Military Skills" written by Sun-szi, who lived in the

VI-V centuries BC. Although Sun-szi's treatise is mainly devoted to the problems of military skill, it contains interesting views on the military-political activity of the state and the head of state in the field of warfare. According to the author, politics has a dominant role in relation to military work, and the direction of military activity is determined by politics (2, p.31; 14, p.13).

Explaining the nature of wars in his own way, Sun-Tzu said that war is a great task for the state. It is the basis of life and death, the way to destruction or survival. (2, p.16).

The ideas contained in Sun-Tzu's treatise on the generalization and study of military practice were somehow continued and completed in the treatise written by U-szu, another thinker of ancient China. His work also focuses on military skills and the conduct of battles. However, in this work there are many opinions about the military policy of the state leadership, the nature of wars and the reasons for their outbreak. According to U-szu, wars took place in the following cases: 1) for the sake of fame; 2) to obtain benefits; 3) to resolve accumulated grievances; 4) because of unrest in the country and 5) because of famine. That is, according to the author, the rulers waged wars for these reasons. (3)

The works of ancient Greek and Roman thinkers are a new page in the development of military science to understand the nature of war and to study the activities of rulers in connection with war. The high development of martial arts in the Greek and Roman states, the special role of wars in socio-political life did not escape the notice of thinkers of the time, and interesting ideas and considerations about the nature of war has emerged. Although the political nature of the war is not properly revealed in these views and considerations, certain new ideas have been put forward about the responsibilities and duties of the military-political leadership of the state in connection with the conduct of wars. In this regard, conclusions and generalizations of the

Greek philosophers and thinkers Socrates (V-IV centuries BC), Thucydides (460-396 BC), Herodotus (484-425 BC), Xenophon (430-354 BC), Plato (427-347 BC), Aristotle (384-322 BC), the Roman thinker Cicero (106-43 BC) and others are of scientific and historical importance for tracing the history of the development of military thought.

Socrates attributed the cause of wars to the inner qualities of the people. According to him, the main causes of war are human imperfection, the inability to distinguish between good and evil, as well as the violation of the rule of law within the state due to the fault of the rulers. Among the ideas of Socrates are those that call people to tolerance (4). According to the ancient Greek philosopher Plato, war is a natural state of nations, and therefore wars are both necessary and inevitable (5, p.10). In other words, as noted by experts, Plato put forward an idea that served to perpetuate war in human life. The Greek philosopher distinguished two types of wars, which he regarded as the natural state of nations - civil and foreign wars. Civil wars have no special place in Plato's theory. He did not consider the conflicts between the Greeks as a war. According to him, the war was a military confrontation between the Greeks and the barbarians. Plato regarded foreign wars as the greatest form of war, and he had a special respect for those who showed courage in such wars (6, p.7).

There are a number of interesting ideas about the nature of wars in Aristotle's works. First of all, he is the author of the "just war" concept. According to him, the main goal of just wars is to achieve peace and development (7, p.9). Aristotle also considered the wars for slaves to be a "just war" (5, p.10).

Aristotle also divided wars into two types - civil and foreign wars. He saw civil wars as conflicts within the Greeks, and foreign wars as wars with barbaric neighbors. Aristotle, who justified wars, said that they encouraged people to be just and restrained, and that living in peace would lead them astray. (4).

Similar ideas can be found in the writings of ancient Roman thinkers. For example, according to Marcus Cicero (106-43 BC), the beginning of wars stems from the qualities inherited in human nature, that is, the desire to get rich and the desire for power. According to the author, these passions forced people to engage in armed conflict. Cicero added that human nature is not capable of avoiding war, it can only be included in the normative framework of human culture. According to Cicero, the formation of such a culture required great effort and hard work on the part of the people. It was assumed that after such efforts, people could determine the legal norms of warfare. (8).

In the early Middle Ages, when Christianity had a strong influence in the West, it is possible to observe the strengthening of religious views on the nature of wars and their conduct. For example, the IV century theologian of Milan, Amvrosi (340-397) sought to explain wars from a religious point of view and called on Christians to take part in wars to protect them from religious infidels (7, p.10). Attempts to explain the war by religious factors were later continued in the views of the Christian theologians Aurelius Augustine (354-

430) and Isidore of Seville (? -636). They and their followers gave a new religious meaning to the concept of "just war". According to these views, war should be waged when there was no other choice, the war should be waged to restore justice, the return of looted property, and the decision to start a war should be made by statesmen, not individuals (9).

The idea of linking the essence of wars with religion can be observed in the works of the 11th century oriental literary monuments "Siyasatname" (Policy Paper) (10) and "Gabusname" (11). The "Siyasatname" was written by Abu Ali Hasan ibn Ali Khaja Nizamulmulk, a vizier of the Seljuk rulers of the 11th century. Nizamulmulk, who has extensive experience in statehood, also commented on state and military issues in his advice on public administration. Neither the "Gabusname" nor the "Siyasatname" has a separate opinion on the nature of wars. However, the general content of these works suggests that both authors linked the beginning of wars and their conduct with religious destiny.

Amir Teymur (1336-1405) (Tamerlane), one of the great commanders and rulers of the military history of the East and the world, also linked the emergence of wars with religious origins, destiny, and pointed to its eternity. In the "Tuzuk"s (testaments) which are attributed to this great commander, Amir Teymur not only linked wars to religious destiny, but also to the need to establish peace in countries where oppression and violence took place and where Sharia law was not observed. That is why he considered it necessary for powerful rulers like him to intervene and start a war to end injustice in countries where the rule of law has weakened and disappeared. (12, p.89-91).

Machiavelli and European thinkers about wars

It is possible to witness the special attention paid to the study of military knowledge in Europe from the XV-XVI centuries. Among the intellectuals and thinkers of this period, the name of the Italian political thinker Niccolo Machiavelli (1469-1527) should be noted. Machiavelli, who wrote a serious work on the subject of the military, *The Art of War*, saw the emergence and conduct of wars as a normal within his vision. According to him, one of the main tasks of the state and the rulers was to keep the wars in constant focus. Machiavelli wrote that the policy of the state should be aimed at achieving two main goals - 1) the acquisition of new territories and 2) the preservation of their freedom. Machiavelli did not consider it right to impose any restrictions on wars. The author noted that states must be able to wage war and be ready for it, because the victory brings honor and prestige to the state. Machiavelli wrote that a wise ruler should think of nothing but war, the rules of war, the science of war, and that waging war is a task that the ruler should not entrust to anyone else. (13, p.32).

According to Erasmus Rotterdamski (1466-1536), a Dutch thinker who was a contemporary of Machiavelli, the beginning of wars was caused by a decline in the level of morality and intellect among people. E. Rotterdamski saw the monarchs as the cause of wars and called on them to reconcile their interests in war

and peace with the interests of the people. Therefore, he considered it important to subordinate foreign policy to the interests of the people, to strengthen borders to prevent wars and to expand trade relations between nations. The Dutch thinker was of the opinion that while the measures taken did not prevent wars, they could at least minimize them. (4).

The French philosopher Jean Bodin (1530-1596) sought to find the causes of war in the military and considered war to be harmful to the state and human society (4). The German theologian Sebastian Frank (1499-1542) also linked the wars to subjective factors and the will of the people. Frank stated that people must wage war against wars in order to achieve peace, and he called such wars holy wars (15, p.12).

Since the 17th to the 18th centuries, European countries entered a new stage of economic development. This development led to political activism, as well as opened a new page in the development of socio-political thought. From that period, a revival has been seen in the development of martial arts. The specific historical conditions were also accompanied by the emergence of new theories of war, the emergence of new ideas and considerations about the role of the state in wars.

Thomas Hobbes (1588-1679), one of the philosophers and thinkers of this period, expressed his hatred of war, but also put forward the idea of its permanence. He attributed the start of wars to the imperfection of the human mind, the imperfection of the public consciousness, and did not rule out the presence of political elements. According to T. Hobbes, it was the desire to compete, distrust and gain fame that led people to war (6, p.10).

In the works of the XVII and XVIII century philosophers Charles Louis Montesquieu (1689-1755) and Jean-Jacques Russo (1712-1778), one can find some interesting ideas about the nature of wars. For example, Jean-Jacques Rousseau, saw wars as a result of civil society dominated by private property. According to him, as long as there is private property, which creates inequality, there will be wars (8).

The works of classical German philosophers of the XVIII century and special contributions I.Kant (1724-1804) and Hegel (1770-1831) who had a special contribution to the development of philosophical thought, also contain a number of ideas about the nature of war. Kant described the natural state of people as a state of war. Kant also saw the instability of the internal situation in the country as one of the reasons for the war. According to Kant, a state ruled by lawlessness and injustice would always try to interfere with its neighbors. He saw one of the reasons for the war in interstate relations. According to him, many states were trying to occupy the territory of another state in order to ensure lasting peace, which led to wars. In order to prevent wars that threaten humanity, Kant considered it necessary to establish lawful relations between states and to enlighten and morally improve people (5).

Unlike Kant, Hegel did not believe in the possibility of lasting peace between peoples and states, and tried to reveal the essence of war by applying a new method. According to him, a possible lasting peace

could lead to stagnation in all spheres of life. On the other hand, development required a periodic movement among people. According to Hegel, wars arose from the nature of existing ones, and he saw these wars as a matter of protecting the spiritual health of nations. He believed that warring states would be strengthened, that internal strife would be prevented, and that nations would be more united. (5).

Jomini and Clausewitz's theories about wars

The rapid development of socio-political thought from the XVIII century laid the foundation for the formation of military science as a separate field. The separate formation of this field of science was also associated with the rapid development of martial arts, the need to develop a scientific and theoretical basis for the success of the growing mass wars. From this point of view, the XVIII and XIX centuries can be characterized as a period of revival of military science, military-scientific knowledge. Among the military thinkers of this period were the English general Heinrich Lloyd (1756-1763), the German Henry Dietrich Byulov (1757-1807) and the Austrian military man Erzerg Karl (1771-1847). In their writings, these generals focused more on war and martial arts. However, their work is of particular importance in raising military science and military thought to a new level (6, p.69).

The study of the nature and essence of wars has been raised to a qualitatively new level in the works of Henry Jomini (1779-1869) and Karl Clausewitz (1780-1831), who were at the height of world military-scientific thought in the nineteenth century. H. Jomini for a first time among military thinkers tried to create a theory that could shed light on all areas of military work. He tried to formulate his theory through the prism of martial arts, and therefore his military-scientific research was dominated by issues of martial arts, and he even envisioned war politics as one of the principles of martial arts. It is clear from the author's subsequent explanations that the principle of war policy refers to the political nature of the war, and that this area is more relevant to the activities of state rulers. In other words, H. Jomini pointed to the political connection of war at the beginning of his famous work "The Art of War" (16, p.7).

Jomini paid close attention to assessing the nature of the state's policy in determining the nature of wars. Jomini unequivocally accepted that wars were started by states. According to him, states engaged in wars in the following cases:

- To reclaim certain rights or to defend them;
- To protect and maintain the great interests of the state, as commerce, manufactures, or agriculture;
- To uphold neighboring states whose existence is necessary either for the safety of the government or the balance of power;
- To fulfill the obligations of offensive and defensive alliances;
- To propagate political or religious theories, to crush them out, or to defend them;
- To increase the influence and power of the state by acquisitions of territory;

-To defend the threatened independence of the state;

-To avenge insulted honor; or,

-From a mania for conquest (16, p.9).

H. Jomini also distinguished the following types of war: offensive wars to reclaim rights, of wars defensive politically, and offensive in a military point of view, wars of expediency, of wars with or without allies, wars of Intervention, aggressive wars for conquest and other reasons, wars of opinion, national wars, civil wars, and wars of religion, double wars, and the danger of undertaking two wars at once (16, p10-26).

A more complete definition of wars can be found in Clausewitz's famous work on war. This work is a vivid expression of Clausewitz's lifelong research and experience, and remains one of the most valuable works on war in the world to date. Clausewitz, who achieved more serious and scientific generalizations by studying and continuing the military knowledge that existed before him, remains one of the greatest representatives of the history of world military thought. Clausewitz's theoretical legacy is one of the main sources cited today in the study of a number of areas of military work. In fact Clausewitz's work can be considered the culmination and higher level of the history of military thought before him. Therefore, Clausewitz's scientific and theoretical work remains relevant up today.

One of Clausewitz's greatest contributions to the history of military thought was his insights into the nature of war. In Clausewitz's view, the war was not a separate activity, but a continuation of political relations. According to him political relations did not end with the outbreak of war, and these relations did not turn into anything else. On the contrary, regardless of the nature of the force means, this policy was essentially continued. Comparing the war to diplomatic activity, Clausewitz wrote that the submission of diplomatic notes and letters does not end diplomatic relations between states and peoples. The war was another continuation of the ideas reflected in diplomatic documents (17, p.377).

Clausewitz argued that war could never be considered in isolation from political relations. If this were attempted, the ropes linking war and politics would be broken, and illogical conclusions could emerge. It was said that politics, by turning the horrors of war into an ordinary weapon, demanded that all forces be mobilized to raise this weapon. Since war is an integral part of politics, it has to accept the nature of this policy. If politics becomes more widespread and frightening, then war also expands and becomes more dangerous (17, p.379).

Clarifying his views, Clausewitz put forward the following concepts related to the essence of war:

- war is an act of violence an act of violence intended to compel our opponents to fulfil our will

- War is nothing but a continuation of political intercourse, with a mixture of other means

- War is not only a political act, but also a real weapon of politics (18, p.34,35).

According to Clausewitz, it is not right to make politics dependent on the war. Because politics provokes war, and if politics is perceived as intelligence,

war is its weapon. Clausewitz wrote that war does not happen suddenly and that it is impossible to ignite it at once. War emerges as a continuation of a long-standing policy (16, p.381).

When Clausewitz spoke of politics, he was referring to a policy aimed at protecting the interests of the state on the basis of certain norms, rather than personal interests, the implementation of individual claims, and the activities of judges subjected to ambition. In order to clarify the nature of wars, he also tried to clarify the nature of such a policy.

Towards the end of the XIX century and the beginning of the XX century, German Field Marshal Henry Moltke (1800-1891), French Marshal Ferdinand Foch (1851-1929), Alfred Schlieffen (1833-1913), and Hans Delbrueck (1848-1929) contributed to the development of military thought and the formation of military science. These servicemen had a rich military experience, holding high military positions for a long time. Therefore, in the works of these military theorists, practical issues, more actual issues of military art of the time are more widely covered, and in their works, war-politics, war-state policy issues have not been the subject of such a broad analysis. Only Field Marshal H. Moltke devoted some space to military and political issues in his famous work "War Exercises" (Moltke's *Kriegslehren*). However, in this case, he could not bring anything new to the views expressed by Clausewitz (19, p.9).

Socialist theory of wars

From the second half of the XIX century, the socialist theory of war began to take shape. This theory is associated with the names of Karl Marx and Friedrich Engels. The conclusions reached by Marx and Engels in defining the nature of wars and armies were regarded as a theory that even revolutionized Soviet military science. The socialist ideologues claimed that Marx and Engels, by criticizing the pre-existing military-theoretical knowledge, applied the materialist-dialectical method to them, laid the foundation of the objective science of war and peace, and developed a methodology for solving problems related to these issues. (20, p.7).

In the military-theoretical ideas of K. Marx and F. Engels, the views on the nature and causes of wars, the connection of war with politics, the classification of wars were written through class conflict. For example, according to them, the emergence of wars was associated with the emergence of class societies, private property. Marx and Engels emphasized that the strengthening of the exploitative nature of private property, the sharpening of contradictions within the exploiting society, and the more aggressive orientation of the results of material production in their time were the main causes of war. At the same time, they believed that the elimination of class society, private property would end the war. According to Marx and Engels, class inequality and antagonistic relations arising from class inequality within society were the main reasons for the outbreak of wars. They also think that the policy that led to the war, accompanied by armed violence, was rooted in the inequality created by the economic rela-

tions of the exploiting society (private property). According to Marx and Engels, the cause of wars must be rooted in the economy regardless why it is started. In other words, inequality in economic relations eventually led to sharp confrontation and war. For example, Engels stated that violence is a means of war. The goal is to gain economic benefits (21, p.18-19).

The theoretical approach of Lenin (1870-1924), characterized as a new stage of Marxism, is also characterized by a class approach to the definition and classification of wars, their causes and driving forces. It is known that the theory of socialism, founded by Marx and Engels, was continued by Lenin and raised to a new level. He was characterized as a great theorist and strategist of the socialist structure of society and the proletarian revolution in the former Soviet military-historical literature (22, p.3).

Lenin described the war as a continuation of politics by force, and stated that the basis of this idea was formed by Clausewitz. He regarded Clausewitz as one of the most profound philosophers on military issues, and wrote that Marxists rightly based Clausewitz's popular view of war on the nature of wars (23, p.417-434).

According to the scientific and historical literature, although Lenin accepted the opinion of the German general and war philosopher K. Clausewitz that "war is a continuation of politics by other means", he replaced the phrase "by other means" with "violent means" and improved his thinking. But Lenin did more than improve one expression. He also approached Clausewitz's definition of war from a different perspective.

Actually, the fact that war is an act of violence is also presented by Clausewitz. He stated that "war is an act of violence to force the enemy to carry out our will" (18, p.34) and that Lenin's definition of war was a combination of Clausewitz's view that "war is a continuation of politics by other means." Even in some of Lenin's works, he simply repeated Clausewitz's famous idea and presented war as a continuation of politics by other means (24, p.75-106). In other words, from a formal point of view, there is no difference between Clausewitz's definition of war and Lenin's definition of war. The difference is in the content behind each of them. In Clausewitz' view, the policy that led to the war was a continuation of the foreign policy of the states. He saw the war as a continuation of the state's foreign policy pursued by other means, such as the use of the army. In Lenin's view, the policy that led to the war was a policy based on private property and the existing economic relations, which were exploited and intensified between the exploiting classes.

In other words, according to Lenin, the cause of the war was the aggravation of socio-political relations in the context of private property, the complication of relations between classes, the intensification of conflicts between the exploited and being exploited, and its reflection in domestic politics. It was stated that in a class (stratified) society, the country's domestic policy reflected the interests of the ruling class (stratum), so this policy had a strong influence on the nature and character of the country's foreign policy. It was the desire to secure the interests of the ruling classes that led

to the war. Lenin unequivocally linked the beginning of the war with class interests, and saw the way to its elimination in the destruction of class society. In this sense, the term "violent means" in the phrase "war is a continuation of politics by force" was given a special meaning by Lenin, and this meaning was associated with class struggle. For example, if this expression was replaced by "means of force", then Lenin's term "means of violence" would have lost its political meaning. Because "means of force" could mean a legitimate army organized and maintained by the state, "violence" meant only a violent organization that serves the interests of the ruling class and is armed to ensure the interests of the ruling class. Therefore, the destruction of class society, the abolition of private property, and the destruction of the army, which was an organization of violence from one class to another, was considered to be the main conditions for eliminating the causes of wars. Lenin saw the way to achieve this in the class struggle, in the destruction of the property class and the state that reflected their interests, in the creation of a proletarian dictatorship that would destroy this state (25, p.373, 417).

Thus, Lenin and his advisers began to fight for the establishment of the socialist revolution in the whole country against the private owners, who made up almost half of the population of a large country like Russia. This struggle was not only a political, ideological, economic and moral struggle, but also a military. The Bolsheviks, led by Lenin, were able to gain the upper hand in this struggle through great massacres. The Bolshevik government was not only established in Russia, but also spread to the countries that had once declared independence from Russia through war. As a result, the requirements of Lenin's doctrine of war were implemented in both Russia and the Russian-occupied republics, and were accepted as the dominant ideology. That is, by inciting the civil war in the country, the private property class was destroyed and the power of the proletarian dictatorship based on weapons was established.

New approaches on wars

As long as the Soviet Union and the socialist front existed, Lenin's theory of war continued to be an integral part of socialist theory. After the collapse of the Soviet Union and the end of the socialist front, new views on the socialist theory of war emerged. In particular, the military-political processes, wars and military conflicts that have taken place in the world in recent decades have given rise to many new ideas about the definition of war. It should be distinctly noted that Clausewitz's famous definition remains the leading thesis for defining the essence of war. However, the emergence of new approaches, ideas and thoughts on the nature of war reveal naturally. As war is such a complex and multifaceted socio-political event that it is impossible to cover all its nature and aspects in a simple definition. On the other hand, the methods and means of warfare are changing in contemporary world. Most of the regional wars in recent years have been fought by non-state actors and are taking place on a smaller scale. At the same time, the use of asymmetric wars has increased. These also require further clarification of the

concept of war in the academic literature. The emergence of new ideas and concepts for a deeper understanding of the nature of war is also related to this need.

It is impossible to comment all the ideas in one article and concepts put forward by various authors on the definition of war in recent years. There are many of them (26; 27; 28; 29) and only a few of them should be paid attention to.

The Law of War Manual, prepared by The Department of Defense in 2015, describes the nature of war as follows: "War has been described as a violent clash of interests characterized by the use of force. The fact that violence is an essential element of war has been viewed as important in understanding the nature of war. The violent nature of war has also meant that suffering has been an unfortunate and tragic, but unavoidable consequence of war" (30, p.16-17).

"The Theory of War and Strategy", prepared by The United States War College, refers to the Doctrine for the Armed Forces of the United States when defining war. "War is the socially sanctioned violence to achieve political goals," the document said. Then it adds, "The character of war, however, may radically change over time, highly dependent as it is on scientific innovation, technological changes, demographic shifts, international affairs, and national policies. Each war thus possesses its own distinct character, rooted in the context of its time and place, yet simultaneously shares a common nature with military conflicts from all eras" (31 p.13)

The Working Group for Research on the Causes of War (AKUF) at the University of Hamburg described the war as an act of violence and said it had the following characteristics:

1. "Two or more armed forces are participating in the fighting, at least one of which are regular fighting forces (military, paramilitary units, police) of the government;
2. There must be a minimum of central control of the fighters on both sides, even if this manifests itself as organized armed defense or planned assaults (guerrilla operations, partisan war, etc.);
3. Armed operations continue and are not occasional, spontaneous clashes; i.e. both sides operate according to a planned strategy regardless of whether fighting takes place on the territory of one or more societies and of how long they take" (32)

According to another study, the following characteristics determine the nature of war:

- war is a social event, an independent sphere of public life, a special social reality;
- war is a macro-social contradiction in a society that has lost its interconnectedness;
- at least two subjects take part in the war;
- the goals and objectives of these subjects are contradictory;
- Insufficient resources are needed to achieve these goals;
- In war, armed means of violence are massively used by the opposing sides. (15, p.27).

The signs described in each of these definitions relate to war and can serve as a starting point for clarifying the nature of war. However, these signs mostly reflect the special aspects, details and specific circumstances of the war. They are not enough to form a general understanding of war.

From this point of view, the following concept is somewhat characteristic to reflect and generalize all aspects of war: war is a socio-political event, a socio-political, economic, ideological, as well as national, religious, territorial between states, peoples, nations, classes and social groups and is one of the forms of resolving other conflicts by means of military violence (33, p.233-235).

In terms of clarifying the nature of wars, this definition attracts more attention. Because this definition reflects the political essence of the war, its subjects and means. It is noted that economic, ideological, national, religious, territorial and other contradictions can also cause war. But it must be borne in mind that economic, religious and national differences between states and peoples do not in themselves lead to war. The essence and character of the policy formed and pursued by the state, nation, social groups on economic, religious, national and other grounds leads to war. It would not be right to isolate any cause of war from politics. In other words, Clausewitz's definition remains the main approach in determining the nature of wars.

The use of the term "military violence" mentioned in this definition as "military force and violence" would be correct in terms of a clearer definition of the means of war. Because "military violence" is more of a term that can refer to illegitimate means of force, including terrorist groups and illegal mercenaries. It is true that the processes taking place in the modern world also show that states use such means to achieve their goals. However the most typical tool for war is legitimate military force. As a rule, only the experience of waging war with the widespread use of legitimate means of force manifests itself.

Conclusion

Summarizing the above, it is possible to conclude that the war is also a socio-political event under the leadership and organization of the state with the use of legitimate means of force to prevent military aggression against the national interests of the country. This definition allows us to draw the right conclusions to assess the nature of wars involving more aggressed countries. Undoubtedly, one of the valid ways to prevent such wars is to develop a realistic policy and ensure its effective implementation for the country's military security. In order to find an effective way to protect against the terrible devastation of war and to ensure national military security, it is necessary to properly clarify the essence and nature of war. From the earliest times, intellectuals have tried to express their thoughts and ideas in this direction. One of the most pressing issues facing military science today is to clarify the nature of war and to provide a clear definition. The ideas and proposals put forward help to understand new aspects of the nature of war. However, these ideas and

proposals do not refute Clausewitz's definition of war, but rather complement it.

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